

A miniature **Bio**-photonics **C**ompanion **D**iagnostics platform for reliable cancer diagnosis and treatment monitoring.

Research and Innovation Action (RIA)
Information & Communication Technologies (ICT)
G.A. no: 732309
Web-site: <http://biocdx.eu/>

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Survey on end-users' requirements.

PoC device for cancer early diagnosis & treatment monitoring.

Stakeholders' requirements & needs

With approximately 14 million new cases, 8.2 million cancer related deaths, and 32.6 million people living with cancer in 2012, cancer represents the leading cause of death worldwide, killing more people than HIV/ AIDS, malaria and tuberculosis combined. The number of new cases is expected to rise from 14 million to 22 million by 2030; this is about a 70% increase in only two decades and the number of global cancer deaths is projected to increase by 45% in the period from 2007 to 2030 (Source: World Health Organization¹)

Despite these predictions, the World Health Organization (WHO) states that many cancers can be reduced, and patients to have a high chance to be cured if cancer is detected early and treated adequately, through the personalized management of the patients while there is a growing consensus among clinicians and investigators that this is the only viable defense against cancer morbidity.

Aiming to identify the medical needs and define the requirements and the intended use of a Point of Care (PoC) device for early cancer diagnosis and treatment monitoring like the one which is under development in BIOCDx (G.A. no: 732309), an "Expert Opinion Check" field survey has been conducted.

In this framework, a survey questionnaire has been designed and distributed to doctors and clinicians, including possible demands of the final users regarding a miniaturized, ultra-sensitive and reliable PoC device for the monitoring of cancer biomarkers in body fluids and specifically in whole blood samples.

The questionnaire composed of 38 open, semi-open, and ranking questions covering:

- Field of expertise and role of the participant.
- Intended use and application of a new PoC device.
- Needs/requirements related to the testing procedure using a PoC device.
- Technical requirements from a PoC device.
- Financial and cost aspects.

¹ World Health Organization. Cancer Fact sheet N°297. 2015 (<http://www.who.int/mediacentre/factsheets/fs297/en/>).

Survey Findings

Application

Which cancer types are you interested in?

22 responses

Do you want to detect many biomarkers simultaneously?

22 responses

How many biomarkers you want to detect?

22 responses

For you application, would you prefer a disposable cartridge?

22 responses

How long you want to store the cartridge?

22 responses

You are interested in:

20 responses

Test

Needs/requirements related to the testing procedure using a PoC device for cancer treatment monitoring and/or cancer diagnosis

How long you want to store the cartridge?

22 responses

How many samples do you want to test per day (the speed of the analysis)?

21 responses

What analysis duration do you expect?

21 responses

Which maximal sample volume do you tolerate for each analysis?

21 responses

Which sample type do you want to analyse?

21 responses

How many preparation steps would you tolerate?

20 responses

How many preparation steps you perform in your work for a standard analysis?

19 responses

What is the qualification level of the operator to use the instrument?

Which time to result do you expect from such a test?

14 responses

What Sensitivity do you expect from such a measurement?

14 responses

What Specificity do you expect from such a measurement?

14 responses

Instrument / Device

Do you want an automated system?

22 responses

What's the degree of automation?

22 responses

What connectivity would you prefer?

20 responses

What kind of result do you prefer?

Cost

Which price you are able to pay for the system?

19 responses

What is the cost per test you can accept?

19 responses

BIOCDx Device/ End-users Questionnaire

This is a survey on end-users requirements and needs from a Point-of-Care (PoC) device for cancer detection.

Email address *

[REDACTED]

End-user information

Organization/Company name *

[REDACTED]

Role - Field of expertise *

Medical Oncology

Country

Greece

Questionnaire

Application

Which cancer types are you interested in?

- Breast
- Prostate
- Lung
- GI tract
- Hematopoietic malignancies
- Skin
- Soft tissue sarcomas
- Melanoma
- Brain
- Urinary tract

Do you want to detect many biomarkers simultaneously?

- Yes
- No

How many biomarkers you want to detect?

- 1 biomarker
- < 5 biomarkers

For you application, would you prefer a disposable cartridge? *

- Yes
- No

How long you want to store the cartridge? *

- < 3 months
- 3 months < <6 months
- > 6 months

Do you prefer to reuse the cartridge?

- Yes
- No

If you prefer to reuse the cartridge. How many times?

- 1 < <5
- 5 < <10
- 10 < <20

You are interested in:

- Progression
- Relapse
- Early diagnosis
- Therapeutic response
- Other: _____

Test

How many samples do you want to test per day (the speed of the analysis)?

- < 50
- < 250
- < 500
- < 1000
- Other: _____

What analysis duration do you expect?

- < 5 min
- < 1 hour
- < 5 hours
- < 10 hours
- Other: _____

Which maximal sample volume do you tolerate for each analysis?

- < 5 μL
- < 100 μL
- < 500 μL
- < 1 mL
- Other: _____

Which sample type do you want to analyse?

- Whole Blood
- Plasma
- Serum
- Other: _____

Do you prefer a specific sample type?

Whole Blood

Plasma

Serum

Other: _____

Do you prefer a specific coagulant?

Yes

No

If yes, which coagulant do you prefer?

Li-Hep

K2-EDTA

K3-EDTA

Citrate

Other: _____

What is the cost per test you can accept?

< 1 Euro

< 10 Euro

< 100 Euro

< 1000 Euro

How many preparation steps would you tolerate?

- < 2
- < 5
- < 10
- > 10
- Other: _____

How many preparation steps you perform in your work for a standard analysis?

- < 2
- < 5
- < 10
- > 10
- Other: _____

Which preparation steps do you tolerate?

What is the qualification level of the operator to use the instrument?

	Yes	No
Lab technician	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Lab engineer	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Clinician	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

If your answer is Other. Please specify.

What level of user experience do you expect?

Trained expert only

Simple use for non-trained personnel

At which cost you can buy the detection kit?

< 100 Euro

100 < < 500 Euro

500 < < 1000 Euro

> 1000 Euro

Which time to result do you expect from such a test?

few hours

What Sensitivity do you expect from such a measurement?

high

What Specificity do you expect from such a measurement?

>90 %

Instrument / Device

Do you want an automated system?

Yes

No

What's the degree of automation?

Manual

Semi- Automated

Fully-Automated

Do you want a point of care device?

Yes

No

Do you need the device to be transportable?

Yes

No

What system dimensions you accept?

Handheld (15x10x15 cm)

POC (20x15x20 cm)

Microwave (40x40x40 cm)

I don't care

What connectivity would you prefer?

LAN (local area network)

WLAN (Wireless local area network)

Other: _____

What system weight you accept?

- < 2 kg
- < 5 kg
- < 15 kg
- I don't care

Which price you are able to pay for the system?

- < 5 KEuro
- < 10 KEuro
- < 20 KEuro
- Other: _____

Which sensitivity you are targeting?

- μM
- nM
- pM
- fM

You need a fixed temperature?

- Yes
- No

If Yes. Which temperature?

< 25 C _____

If No. Which temperature range?

- 4< <25 Celsius
- 15< <40 Celsius
- 15< <60 Celsius
- 15< <90 Celsius
- Other: _____

What kind of result do you prefer?

	Yes	No
Semi-quantitative	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Quantitative	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Questions for policy makers / finances

Health insurances. Would you prefer to finance

- Sensor device (investment)
- Sensor chips (consumable)

Hospital/Lab administration

	Yes	No
Selection (bidding procedure) and purchase procedures for new equipment?	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

BIOCDx Device/ End-users Questionnaire

This is a survey on end-users requirements and needs from a Point-of-Care (PoC) device for cancer detection.

Email address *

[REDACTED]

End-user information

Organization/Company name *

[REDACTED]

Role - Field of expertise *

Clinical Chemist

Country

Netherlands

Questionnaire

Application

Which cancer types are you interested in?

- Breast
- Prostate
- Lung
- GI tract
- Hematopoietic malignancies
- Skin
- Soft tissue sarcomas
- Melanoma
- Brain
- Urinary tract

Do you want to detect many biomarkers simultaneously?

- Yes
- No

How many biomarkers you want to detect?

- 1 biomarker
- < 5 biomarkers

For you application, would you prefer a disposable cartridge? *

- Yes
- No

How long you want to store the cartridge? *

- < 3 months
- 3 months < <6 months
- > 6 months

Do you prefer to reuse the cartridge?

- Yes
- No

If you prefer to reuse the cartridge. How many times?

- 1 < <5
- 5 < <10
- 10 < <20

You are interested in:

- Progression
- Relapse
- Early diagnosis
- Therapeutic response
- Other: _____

Test

How many samples do you want to test per day (the speed of the analysis)?

< 50

< 250

< 500

< 1000

Other: _____

What analysis duration do you expect?

< 5 min

< 1 hour

< 5 hours

< 10 hours

Other: _____

Which maximal sample volume do you tolerate for each analysis?

< 5 μL

< 100 μL

< 500 μL

< 1 mL

Other: 100 for several markers; for 1 marker 500 ul

Which sample type do you want to analyse?

Whole Blood

Plasma

Serum

Other: no preference

Do you prefer a specific sample type?

Whole Blood

Plasma

Serum

Other: no

Do you prefer a specific coagulant?

Yes

No

If yes, which coagulant do you prefer?

Li-Hep

K2-EDTA

K3-EDTA

Citrate

Other: _____

What is the cost per test you can accept?

< 1 Euro

< 10 Euro

< 100 Euro

< 1000 Euro

How many preparation steps would you tolerate?

< 2

< 5

< 10

> 10

Other: _____

How many preparation steps you perform in your work for a standard analysis?

< 2

< 5

< 10

> 10

Other: _____

Which preparation steps do you tolerate?

calibration, quality control

What is the qualification level of the operator to use the instrument?

	Yes	No
Lab technician	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Lab engineer	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Clinician	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Other	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>

If your answer is Other. Please specify.

Clinicians in case of bed-side testing / point-of-care, but for tumor markers probably not required

What level of user experience do you expect?

- Trained expert only
- Simple use for non-trained personnel

At which cost you can buy the detection kit?

- < 100 Euro
- 100 < < 500 Euro
- 500 < < 1000 Euro
- > 1000 Euro

Which time to result do you expect from such a test?

preferably within 1 hour, but at least within 1/2 day

What Sensitivity do you expect from such a measurement?

to rule out than sens (and neg pred value) reaching 100%

What Specificity do you expect from such a measurement?

for followup as high as possible

Instrument / Device

Do you want an automated system?

Yes

No

What's the degree of automation?

Manual

Semi- Automated

Fully-Automated

Do you want a point of care device?

Yes

No

Do you need the device to be transportable?

Yes

No

What system dimensions you accept?

Handheld (15x10x15 cm)

POC (20x15x20 cm)

Microwave (40x40x40 cm)

I don't care

What connectivity would you prefer?

LAN (local area network)

WLAN (Wireless local area network)

Other: _____

What system weight you accept?

- < 2 kg
- < 5 kg
- < 15 kg
- I don't care

Which price you are able to pay for the system?

- < 5 KEuro
- < 10 KEuro
- < 20 KEuro
- Other: also dependent on the number of markers, throughput, etc

Which sensitivity you are targeting?

- μM
- nM
- pM
- fM

You need a fixed temperature?

- Yes
- No

If Yes. Which temperature?

If No. Which temperature range?

4 < <25 Celsius

15 < <40 Celsius

15 < <60 Celsius

15 < <90 Celsius

Other: roomtemperature

What kind of result do you prefer?

	Yes	No
Semi-quantitative	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Quantitative	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Questions for policy makers / finances

Health insurances. Would you prefer to finance

Sensor device (investment)

Sensor chips (consumable)

Hospital/Lab administration

	Yes	No
Selection (bidding procedure) and purchase procedures for new equipment?	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

BIOCDx Device/ End-users Questionnaire

This is a survey on end-users requirements and needs from a Point-of-Care (PoC) device for cancer detection.

Email address *

[REDACTED]

End-user information

Organization/Company name *

[REDACTED]

Role - Field of expertise *

Pathologist, Medical Oncologist

Country

Greece

Questionnaire

Application

Which cancer types are you interested in?

- Breast
- Prostate
- Lung
- GI tract
- Hematopoietic malignancies
- Skin
- Soft tissue sarcomas
- Melanoma
- Brain
- Urinary tract

Do you want to detect many biomarkers simultaneously?

- Yes
- No

How many biomarkers you want to detect?

- 1 biomarker
- < 5 biomarkers

For you application, would you prefer a disposable cartridge? *

- Yes
- No

How long you want to store the cartridge? *

- < 3 months
- 3 months < <6 months
- > 6 months

Do you prefer to reuse the cartridge?

- Yes
- No

If you prefer to reuse the cartridge. How many times?

- 1 < <5
- 5 < <10
- 10 < <20

You are interested in:

- Progression
- Relapse
- Early diagnosis
- Therapeutic response
- Other: _____

Test

How many samples do you want to test per day (the speed of the analysis)?

- < 50
- < 250
- < 500
- < 1000
- Other: _____

What analysis duration do you expect?

- < 5 min
- < 1 hour
- < 5 hours
- < 10 hours
- Other: _____

Which maximal sample volume do you tolerate for each analysis?

- < 5 μL
- < 100 μL
- < 500 μL
- < 1 mL
- Other: _____

Which sample type do you want to analyse?

- Whole Blood
- Plasma
- Serum
- Other: _____

Do you prefer a specific sample type?

Whole Blood

Plasma

Serum

Other: _____

Do you prefer a specific coagulant?

Yes

No

If yes, which coagulant do you prefer?

Li-Hep

K2-EDTA

K3-EDTA

Citrate

Other: _____

What is the cost per test you can accept?

< 1 Euro

< 10 Euro

< 100 Euro

< 1000 Euro

How many preparation steps would you tolerate?

- < 2
- < 5
- < 10
- > 10
- Other: _____

How many preparation steps you perform in your work for a standard analysis?

- < 2
- < 5
- < 10
- > 10
- Other: _____

Which preparation steps do you tolerate?

What is the qualification level of the operator to use the instrument?

	Yes	No
Lab technician	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Lab engineer	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Clinician	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

If your answer is Other. Please specify.

What level of user experience do you expect?

Trained expert only

Simple use for non-trained personnel

At which cost you can buy the detection kit?

< 100 Euro

100 < < 500 Euro

500 < < 1000 Euro

> 1000 Euro

Which time to result do you expect from such a test?

What Sensitivity do you expect from such a measurement?

What Specificity do you expect from such a measurement?

Instrument / Device

Do you want an automated system?

Yes

No

What's the degree of automation?

Manual

Semi- Automated

Fully-Automated

Do you want a point of care device?

Yes

No

Do you need the device to be transportable?

Yes

No

What system dimensions you accept?

Handheld (15x10x15 cm)

POC (20x15x20 cm)

Microwave (40x40x40 cm)

I don't care

What connectivity would you prefer?

LAN (local area network)

WLAN (Wireless local area network)

Other: _____

What system weight you accept?

- < 2 kg
- < 5 kg
- < 15 kg
- I don't care

Which price you are able to pay for the system?

- < 5 KEuro
- < 10 KEuro
- < 20 KEuro
- Other: _____

Which sensitivity you are targeting?

- μM
- nM
- pM
- fM

You need a fixed temperature?

- Yes
- No

If Yes. Which temperature?

If No. Which temperature range?

- 4< <25 Celsius
- 15< <40 Celsius
- 15< <60 Celsius
- 15< <90 Celsius
- Other: _____

What kind of result do you prefer?

	Yes	No
Semi-quantitative	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Quantitative	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Questions for policy makers / finances

Health insurances. Would you prefer to finance

- Sensor device (investment)
- Sensor chips (consumable)

Hospital/Lab administration

	Yes	No
Selection (bidding procedure) and purchase procedures for new equipment?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

BIOCDx Device/ End-users Questionnaire

This is a survey on end-users requirements and needs from a Point-of-Care (PoC) device for cancer detection.

Email address *

[REDACTED]

End-user information

Organization/Company name *

[REDACTED]

Role - Field of expertise *

Resident in Medical Oncology

Country

Greece

Questionnaire

Application

Which cancer types are you interested in?

- Breast
- Prostate
- Lung
- GI tract
- Hematopoietic malignancies
- Skin
- Soft tissue sarcomas
- Melanoma
- Brain
- Urinary tract

Do you want to detect many biomarkers simultaneously?

- Yes
- No

How many biomarkers you want to detect?

- 1 biomarker
- < 5 biomarkers

For you application, would you prefer a disposable cartridge? *

- Yes
- No

How long you want to store the cartridge? *

- < 3 months
- 3 months < <6 months
- > 6 months

Do you prefer to reuse the cartridge?

- Yes
- No

If you prefer to reuse the cartridge. How many times?

- 1 < <5
- 5 < <10
- 10 < <20

You are interested in:

- Progression
- Relapse
- Early diagnosis
- Therapeutic response

Other: _____

Test

How many samples do you want to test per day (the speed of the analysis)?

- < 50
- < 250
- < 500
- < 1000
- Other: _____

What analysis duration do you expect?

- < 5 min
- < 1 hour
- < 5 hours
- < 10 hours
- Other: _____

Which maximal sample volume do you tolerate for each analysis?

- < 5 μL
- < 100 μL
- < 500 μL
- < 1 mL
- Other: _____

Which sample type do you want to analyse?

- Whole Blood
- Plasma
- Serum
- Other: _____

Do you prefer a specific sample type?

Whole Blood

Plasma

Serum

Other: _____

Do you prefer a specific coagulant?

Yes

No

If yes, which coagulant do you prefer?

Li-Hep

K2-EDTA

K3-EDTA

Citrate

Other: _____

What is the cost per test you can accept?

< 1 Euro

< 10 Euro

< 100 Euro

< 1000 Euro

How many preparation steps would you tolerate?

< 2

< 5

< 10

> 10

Other: _____

How many preparation steps you perform in your work for a standard analysis?

< 2

< 5

< 10

> 10

Other: _____

Which preparation steps do you tolerate?

What is the qualification level of the operator to use the instrument?

	Yes	No
Lab technician	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Lab engineer	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Clinician	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

If your answer is Other. Please specify.

What level of user experience do you expect?

Trained expert only

Simple use for non-trained personnel

At which cost you can buy the detection kit?

< 100 Euro

100 < < 500 Euro

500 < < 1000 Euro

> 1000 Euro

Which time to result do you expect from such a test?

1 Day

What Sensitivity do you expect from such a measurement?

maximum

What Specificity do you expect from such a measurement?

>90%

Instrument / Device

Do you want an automated system?

Yes

No

What's the degree of automation?

Manual

Semi- Automated

Fully-Automated

Do you want a point of care device?

Yes

No

Do you need the device to be transportable?

Yes

No

What system dimensions you accept?

Handheld (15x10x15 cm)

POC (20x15x20 cm)

Microwave (40x40x40 cm)

I don't care

What connectivity would you prefer?

LAN (local area network)

WLAN (Wireless local area network)

Other: _____

What system weight you accept?

- < 2 kg
- < 5 kg
- < 15 kg
- I don't care

Which price you are able to pay for the system?

- < 5 KEuro
- < 10 KEuro
- < 20 KEuro
- Other: _____

Which sensitivity you are targeting?

- μM
- nM
- pM
- fM

You need a fixed temperature?

- Yes
- No

If Yes. Which temperature?

37 C _____

If No. Which temperature range?

- 4< <25 Celsius
- 15< <40 Celsius
- 15< <60 Celsius
- 15< <90 Celsius
- Other: _____

What kind of result do you prefer?

	Yes	No
Semi-quantitative	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Quantitative	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Questions for policy makers / finances

Health insurances. Would you prefer to finance

- Sensor device (investment)
- Sensor chips (consumable)

Hospital/Lab administration

	Yes	No
Selection (bidding procedure) and purchase procedures for new equipment?	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

BIOCDx Device/ End-users Questionnaire

This is a survey on end-users requirements and needs from a Point-of-Care (PoC) device for cancer detection.

Email address *

[REDACTED]

End-user information

Organization/Company name *

[REDACTED]

Role - Field of expertise *

Surgical Oncology-Research Scientist

Country

Greece

Questionnaire

Application

Which cancer types are you interested in?

- Breast
- Prostate
- Lung
- GI tract
- Hematopoietic malignancies
- Skin
- Soft tissue sarcomas
- Melanoma
- Brain
- Urinary tract

Do you want to detect many biomarkers simultaneously?

- Yes
- No

How many biomarkers you want to detect?

- 1 biomarker
- < 5 biomarkers

For you application, would you prefer a disposable cartridge? *

- Yes
- No

How long you want to store the cartridge? *

- < 3 months
- 3 months < <6 months
- > 6 months

Do you prefer to reuse the cartridge?

- Yes
- No

If you prefer to reuse the cartridge. How many times?

- 1 < <5
- 5 < <10
- 10 < <20

You are interested in:

- Progression
- Relapse
- Early diagnosis
- Therapeutic response
- Other: _____

Test

How many samples do you want to test per day (the speed of the analysis)?

- < 50
- < 250
- < 500
- < 1000
- Other: _____

What analysis duration do you expect?

- < 5 min
- < 1 hour
- < 5 hours
- < 10 hours
- Other: _____

Which maximal sample volume do you tolerate for each analysis?

- < 5 μL
- < 100 μL
- < 500 μL
- < 1 mL
- Other: <250 μL _____

Which sample type do you want to analyse?

- Whole Blood
- Plasma
- Serum
- Other: _____

Do you prefer a specific sample type?

Whole Blood

Plasma

Serum

Other: _____

Do you prefer a specific coagulant?

Yes

No

If yes, which coagulant do you prefer?

Li-Hep

K2-EDTA

K3-EDTA

Citrate

Other: _____

What is the cost per test you can accept?

< 1 Euro

< 10 Euro

< 100 Euro

< 1000 Euro

How many preparation steps would you tolerate?

< 2

< 5

< 10

> 10

Other: _____

How many preparation steps you perform in your work for a standard analysis?

< 2

< 5

< 10

> 10

Other: _____

Which preparation steps do you tolerate?

What is the qualification level of the operator to use the instrument?

	Yes	No
Lab technician	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Lab engineer	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Clinician	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>

If your answer is Other. Please specify.

What level of user experience do you expect?

Trained expert only

Simple use for non-trained personnel

At which cost you can buy the detection kit?

< 100 Euro

100< <500 Euro

500< <1000 Euro

>1000 Euro

Which time to result do you expect from such a test?

24 h

What Sensitivity do you expect from such a measurement?

>90%

What Specificity do you expect from such a measurement?

>90%

Instrument / Device

Do you want an automated system?

Yes

No

What's the degree of automation?

Manual

Semi- Automated

Fully-Automated

Do you want a point of care device?

Yes

No

Do you need the device to be transportable?

Yes

No

What system dimensions you accept?

Handheld (15x10x15 cm)

POC (20x15x20 cm)

Microwave (40x40x40 cm)

I don't care

What connectivity would you prefer?

LAN (local area network)

WLAN (Wireless local area network)

Other: _____

What system weight you accept?

- < 2 kg
- < 5 kg
- < 15 kg
- I don't care

Which price you are able to pay for the system?

- < 5 KEuro
- < 10 KEuro
- < 20 KEuro
- Other: _____

Which sensitivity you are targeting?

- μM
- nM
- pM
- fM

You need a fixed temperature?

- Yes
- No

If Yes. Which temperature?

If No. Which temperature range?

- 4< <25 Celsius
- 15< <40 Celsius
- 15< <60 Celsius
- 15< <90 Celsius
- Other: _____

What kind of result do you prefer?

	Yes	No
Semi-quantitative	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Quantitative	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Questions for policy makers / finances

Health insurances. Would you prefer to finance

- Sensor device (investment)
- Sensor chips (consumable)

Hospital/Lab administration

	Yes	No
Selection (bidding procedure) and purchase procedures for new equipment?	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

BIOCDx Device/ End-users Questionnaire

This is a survey on end-users requirements and needs from a Point-of-Care (PoC) device for cancer detection.

Email address *

[Redacted]

End-user information

Organization/Company name *

[Redacted]

Role - Field of expertise *

Oncology Department, Intern at Medical Oncology

Country

Greece

Questionnaire

Application

Which cancer types are you interested in?

- Breast
- Prostate
- Lung
- GI tract
- Hematopoietic malignancies
- Skin
- Soft tissue sarcomas
- Melanoma
- Brain
- Urinary tract

Do you want to detect many biomarkers simultaneously?

- Yes
- No

How many biomarkers you want to detect?

- 1 biomarker
- < 5 biomarkers

For you application, would you prefer a disposable cartridge? *

- Yes
- No

How long you want to store the cartridge? *

- < 3 months
- 3 months < <6 months
- > 6 months

Do you prefer to reuse the cartridge?

- Yes
- No

If you prefer to reuse the cartridge. How many times?

- 1 < <5
- 5 < <10
- 10 < <20

You are interested in:

- Progression
- Relapse
- Early diagnosis
- Therapeutic response
- Other: _____

Test

How many samples do you want to test per day (the speed of the analysis)?

- < 50
- < 250
- < 500
- < 1000
- Other: _____

What analysis duration do you expect?

- < 5 min
- < 1 hour
- < 5 hours
- < 10 hours
- Other: _____

Which maximal sample volume do you tolerate for each analysis?

- < 5 μL
- < 100 μL
- < 500 μL
- < 1 mL
- Other: _____

Which sample type do you want to analyse?

- Whole Blood
- Plasma
- Serum
- Other: _____

Do you prefer a specific sample type?

Whole Blood

Plasma

Serum

Other: _____

Do you prefer a specific coagulant?

Yes

No

If yes, which coagulant do you prefer?

Li-Hep

K2-EDTA

K3-EDTA

Citrate

Other: _____

What is the cost per test you can accept?

< 1 Euro

< 10 Euro

< 100 Euro

< 1000 Euro

How many preparation steps would you tolerate?

- < 2
- < 5
- < 10
- > 10
- Other: _____

How many preparation steps you perform in your work for a standard analysis?

- < 2
- < 5
- < 10
- > 10
- Other: _____

Which preparation steps do you tolerate?

What is the qualification level of the operator to use the instrument?

	Yes	No
Lab technician	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Lab engineer	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Clinician	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>

If your answer is Other. Please specify.

What level of user experience do you expect?

Trained expert only

Simple use for non-trained personnel

At which cost you can buy the detection kit?

< 100 Euro

100< <500 Euro

500< <1000 Euro

>1000 Euro

Which time to result do you expect from such a test?

3-4 days

What Sensitivity do you expect from such a measurement?

approx. 80%

What Specificity do you expect from such a measurement?

approx. 90%

Instrument / Device

Do you want an automated system?

Yes

No

What's the degree of automation?

Manual

Semi- Automated

Fully-Automated

Do you want a point of care device?

Yes

No

Do you need the device to be transportable?

Yes

No

What system dimensions you accept?

Handheld (15x10x15 cm)

POC (20x15x20 cm)

Microwave (40x40x40 cm)

I don't care

What connectivity would you prefer?

LAN (local area network)

WLAN (Wireless local area network)

Other: _____

What system weight you accept?

- < 2 kg
- < 5 kg
- < 15 kg
- I don't care

Which price you are able to pay for the system?

- < 5 KEuro
- < 10 KEuro
- < 20 KEuro
- Other: _____

Which sensitivity you are targeting?

- μM
- nM
- pM
- fM

You need a fixed temperature?

- Yes
- No

If Yes. Which temperature?

If No. Which temperature range?

- 4< <25 Celsius
- 15< <40 Celsius
- 15< <60 Celsius
- 15< <90 Celsius
- Other: _____

What kind of result do you prefer?

	Yes	No
Semi-quantitative	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Quantitative	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Questions for policy makers / finances

Health insurances. Would you prefer to finance

- Sensor device (investment)
- Sensor chips (consumable)

Hospital/Lab administration

	Yes	No
Selection (bidding procedure) and purchase procedures for new equipment?	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

BIOCDx Device/ End-users Questionnaire

This is a survey on end-users requirements and needs from a Point-of-Care (PoC) device for cancer detection.

Email address *

End-user information

Organization/Company name *

Role - Field of expertise *

Sub-investigator

Country

Greece

Questionnaire

Application

Which cancer types are you interested in?

- Breast
- Prostate
- Lung
- GI tract
- Hematopoietic malignancies
- Skin
- Soft tissue sarcomas
- Melanoma
- Brain
- Urinary tract

Do you want to detect many biomarkers simultaneously?

- Yes
- No

How many biomarkers you want to detect?

- 1 biomarker
- < 5 biomarkers

For you application, would you prefer a disposable cartridge? *

- Yes
- No

How long you want to store the cartridge? *

- < 3 months
- 3 months < <6 months
- > 6 months

Do you prefer to reuse the cartridge?

- Yes
- No

If you prefer to reuse the cartridge. How many times?

- 1 < <5
- 5 < <10
- 10 < <20

You are interested in:

- Progression
- Relapse
- Early diagnosis
- Therapeutic response
- Other: _____

Test

How many samples do you want to test per day (the speed of the analysis)?

- < 50
- < 250
- < 500
- < 1000
- Other: _____

What analysis duration do you expect?

- < 5 min
- < 1 hour
- < 5 hours
- < 10 hours
- Other: _____

Which maximal sample volume do you tolerate for each analysis?

- < 5 μL
- < 100 μL
- < 500 μL
- < 1 mL
- Other: _____

Which sample type do you want to analyse?

- Whole Blood
- Plasma
- Serum
- Other: _____

Do you prefer a specific sample type?

Whole Blood

Plasma

Serum

Other: _____

Do you prefer a specific coagulant?

Yes

No

If yes, which coagulant do you prefer?

Li-Hep

K2-EDTA

K3-EDTA

Citrate

Other: _____

What is the cost per test you can accept?

< 1 Euro

< 10 Euro

< 100 Euro

< 1000 Euro

How many preparation steps would you tolerate?

< 2

< 5

< 10

> 10

Other: _____

How many preparation steps you perform in your work for a standard analysis?

< 2

< 5

< 10

> 10

Other: _____

Which preparation steps do you tolerate?

What is the qualification level of the operator to use the instrument?

	Yes	No
Lab technician	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Lab engineer	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Clinician	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

If your answer is Other. Please specify.

What level of user experience do you expect?

Trained expert only

Simple use for non-trained personnel

At which cost you can buy the detection kit?

< 100 Euro

100 < <500 Euro

500 < <1000 Euro

>1000 Euro

Which time to result do you expect from such a test?

What Sensitivity do you expect from such a measurement?

What Specificity do you expect from such a measurement?

Instrument / Device

Do you want an automated system?

Yes

No

What's the degree of automation?

Manual

Semi- Automated

Fully-Automated

Do you want a point of care device?

Yes

No

Do you need the device to be transportable?

Yes

No

What system dimensions you accept?

Handheld (15x10x15 cm)

POC (20x15x20 cm)

Microwave (40x40x40 cm)

I don't care

What connectivity would you prefer?

LAN (local area network)

WLAN (Wireless local area network)

Other: _____

What system weight you accept?

- < 2 kg
- < 5 kg
- < 15 kg
- I don't care

Which price you are able to pay for the system?

- < 5 KEuro
- < 10 KEuro
- < 20 KEuro
- Other: _____

Which sensitivity you are targeting?

- μM
- nM
- pM
- fM

You need a fixed temperature?

- Yes
- No

If Yes. Which temperature?

If No. Which temperature range?

- 4< <25 Celsius
- 15< <40 Celsius
- 15< <60 Celsius
- 15< <90 Celsius
- Other: _____

What kind of result do you prefer?

	Yes	No
Semi-quantitative	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Quantitative	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Questions for policy makers / finances

Health insurances. Would you prefer to finance

- Sensor device (investment)
- Sensor chips (consumable)

Hospital/Lab administration

	Yes	No
Selection (bidding procedure) and purchase procedures for new equipment?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

BIOCDx Device/ End-users Questionnaire

This is a survey on end-users requirements and needs from a Point-of-Care (PoC) device for cancer detection.

Email address *

End-user information

Organization/Company name *

Role - Field of expertise *

Country

Questionnaire

Application

Which cancer types are you interested in?

- Breast
- Prostate
- Lung
- GI tract
- Hematopoietic malignancies
- Skin
- Soft tissue sarcomas
- Melanoma
- Brain
- Urinary tract

Do you want to detect many biomarkers simultaneously?

- Yes
- No

How many biomarkers you want to detect?

- 1 biomarker
- < 5 biomarkers

For you application, would you prefer a disposable cartridge? *

- Yes
- No

How long you want to store the cartridge? *

- < 3 months
- 3 months < <6 months
- > 6 months

Do you prefer to reuse the cartridge?

- Yes
- No

If you prefer to reuse the cartridge. How many times?

- 1 < <5
- 5 < <10
- 10 < <20

You are interested in:

- Progression
- Relapse
- Early diagnosis
- Therapeutic response
- Other: _____

Test

How many samples do you want to test per day (the speed of the analysis)?

- < 50
- < 250
- < 500
- < 1000
- Other: _____

What analysis duration do you expect?

- < 5 min
- < 1 hour
- < 5 hours
- < 10 hours
- Other: _____

Which maximal sample volume do you tolerate for each analysis?

- < 5 μL
- < 100 μL
- < 500 μL
- < 1 mL
- Other: _____

Which sample type do you want to analyse?

- Whole Blood
- Plasma
- Serum
- Other: _____

Do you prefer a specific sample type?

Whole Blood

Plasma

Serum

Other: _____

Do you prefer a specific coagulant?

Yes

No

If yes, which coagulant do you prefer?

Li-Hep

K2-EDTA

K3-EDTA

Citrate

Other: _____

What is the cost per test you can accept?

< 1 Euro

< 10 Euro

< 100 Euro

< 1000 Euro

How many preparation steps would you tolerate?

< 2

< 5

< 10

> 10

Other: _____

How many preparation steps you perform in your work for a standard analysis?

< 2

< 5

< 10

> 10

Other: _____

Which preparation steps do you tolerate?

What is the qualification level of the operator to use the instrument?

	Yes	No
Lab technician	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Lab engineer	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Clinician	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

If your answer is Other. Please specify.

What level of user experience do you expect?

Trained expert only

Simple use for non-trained personnel

At which cost you can buy the detection kit?

< 100 Euro

100 < < 500 Euro

500 < < 1000 Euro

> 1000 Euro

Which time to result do you expect from such a test?

What Sensitivity do you expect from such a measurement?

What Specificity do you expect from such a measurement?

Instrument / Device

Do you want an automated system?

- Yes
- No

What's the degree of automation?

- Manual
- Semi- Automated
- Fully-Automated

Do you want a point of care device?

- Yes
- No

Do you need the device to be transportable?

- Yes
- No

What system dimensions you accept?

- Handheld (15x10x15 cm)
- POC (20x15x20 cm)
- Microwave (40x40x40 cm)
- I don't care

What connectivity would you prefer?

- LAN (local area network)
- WLAN (Wireless local area network)
- Other: _____

What system weight you accept?

- < 2 kg
- < 5 kg
- < 15 kg
- I don't care

Which price you are able to pay for the system?

- < 5 KEuro
- < 10 KEuro
- < 20 KEuro
- Other: _____

Which sensitivity you are targeting?

- μM
- nM
- pM
- fM

You need a fixed temperature?

- Yes
- No

If Yes. Which temperature?

If No. Which temperature range?

- 4< <25 Celsius
- 15< <40 Celsius
- 15< <60 Celsius
- 15< <90 Celsius
- Other: _____

What kind of result do you prefer?

	Yes	No
Semi-quantitative	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Quantitative	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Questions for policy makers / finances

Health insurances. Would you prefer to finance

- Sensor device (investment)
- Sensor chips (consumable)

Hospital/Lab administration

	Yes	No
Selection (bidding procedure) and purchase procedures for new equipment?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

BIOCDx Device/ End-users Questionnaire

This is a survey on end-users requirements and needs from a Point-of-Care (PoC) device for cancer detection.

Email address *

End-user information

Organization/Company name *

Role - Field of expertise *

Director

Country

Greece

Questionnaire

Application

Which cancer types are you interested in?

- Breast
- Prostate
- Lung
- GI tract
- Hematopoietic malignancies
- Skin
- Soft tissue sarcomas
- Melanoma
- Brain
- Urinary tract

Do you want to detect many biomarkers simultaneously?

- Yes
- No

How many biomarkers you want to detect?

- 1 biomarker
- < 5 biomarkers

For you application, would you prefer a disposable cartridge? *

- Yes
- No

How long you want to store the cartridge? *

- < 3 months
- 3 months < <6 months
- > 6 months

Do you prefer to reuse the cartridge?

- Yes
- No

If you prefer to reuse the cartridge. How many times?

- 1 < <5
- 5 < <10
- 10 < <20

You are interested in:

- Progression
- Relapse
- Early diagnosis
- Therapeutic response
- Other: _____

Test

How many samples do you want to test per day (the speed of the analysis)?

< 50

< 250

< 500

< 1000

Other: _____

What analysis duration do you expect?

< 5 min

< 1 hour

< 5 hours

< 10 hours

Other: _____

Which maximal sample volume do you tolerate for each analysis?

< 5 μL

< 100 μL

< 500 μL

< 1 mL

Other: _____

Which sample type do you want to analyse?

Whole Blood

Plasma

Serum

Other: _____

Do you prefer a specific sample type?

Whole Blood

Plasma

Serum

Other: _____

Do you prefer a specific coagulant?

Yes

No

If yes, which coagulant do you prefer?

Li-Hep

K2-EDTA

K3-EDTA

Citrate

Other: _____

What is the cost per test you can accept?

< 1 Euro

< 10 Euro

< 100 Euro

< 1000 Euro

How many preparation steps would you tolerate?

- < 2
- < 5
- < 10
- > 10
- Other: _____

How many preparation steps you perform in your work for a standard analysis?

- < 2
- < 5
- < 10
- > 10
- Other: _____

Which preparation steps do you tolerate?

What is the qualification level of the operator to use the instrument?

	Yes	No
Lab technician	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Lab engineer	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Clinician	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

If your answer is Other. Please specify.

What level of user experience do you expect?

Trained expert only

Simple use for non-trained personnel

At which cost you can buy the detection kit?

< 100 Euro

100 < <500 Euro

500 < <1000 Euro

>1000 Euro

Which time to result do you expect from such a test?

What Sensitivity do you expect from such a measurement?

What Specificity do you expect from such a measurement?

Instrument / Device

Do you want an automated system?

Yes

No

What's the degree of automation?

Manual

Semi- Automated

Fully-Automated

Do you want a point of care device?

Yes

No

Do you need the device to be transportable?

Yes

No

What system dimensions you accept?

Handheld (15x10x15 cm)

POC (20x15x20 cm)

Microwave (40x40x40 cm)

I don't care

What connectivity would you prefer?

LAN (local area network)

WLAN (Wireless local area network)

Other: _____

What system weight you accept?

- < 2 kg
- < 5 kg
- < 15 kg
- I don't care

Which price you are able to pay for the system?

- < 5 KEuro
- < 10 KEuro
- < 20 KEuro
- Other: _____

Which sensitivity you are targeting?

- μM
- nM
- pM
- fM

You need a fixed temperature?

- Yes
- No

If Yes. Which temperature?

If No. Which temperature range?

- 4< <25 Celsius
- 15< <40 Celsius
- 15< <60 Celsius
- 15< <90 Celsius
- Other: _____

What kind of result do you prefer?

	Yes	No
Semi-quantitative	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Quantitative	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Questions for policy makers / finances

Health insurances. Would you prefer to finance

- Sensor device (investment)
- Sensor chips (consumable)

Hospital/Lab administration

	Yes	No
Selection (bidding procedure) and purchase procedures for new equipment?	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>

BIOCDx Device/ End-users Questionnaire

This is a survey on end-users requirements and needs from a Point-of-Care (PoC) device for cancer detection.

Email address *

End-user information

Organization/Company name *

Role - Field of expertise *

Sub-Investigator

Country

Greece

Questionnaire

Application

Which cancer types are you interested in?

- Breast
- Prostate
- Lung
- GI tract
- Hematopoietic malignancies
- Skin
- Soft tissue sarcomas
- Melanoma
- Brain
- Urinary tract

Do you want to detect many biomarkers simultaneously?

- Yes
- No

How many biomarkers you want to detect?

- 1 biomarker
- < 5 biomarkers

For you application, would you prefer a disposable cartridge? *

- Yes
- No

How long you want to store the cartridge? *

- < 3 months
- 3 months < <6 months
- > 6 months

Do you prefer to reuse the cartridge?

- Yes
- No

If you prefer to reuse the cartridge. How many times?

- 1 < <5
- 5 < <10
- 10 < <20

You are interested in:

- Progression
- Relapse
- Early diagnosis
- Therapeutic response
- Other: _____

Test

How many samples do you want to test per day (the speed of the analysis)?

- < 50
- < 250
- < 500
- < 1000
- Other: _____

What analysis duration do you expect?

- < 5 min
- < 1 hour
- < 5 hours
- < 10 hours
- Other: _____

Which maximal sample volume do you tolerate for each analysis?

- < 5 μL
- < 100 μL
- < 500 μL
- < 1 mL
- Other: _____

Which sample type do you want to analyse?

- Whole Blood
- Plasma
- Serum
- Other: _____

Do you prefer a specific sample type?

Whole Blood

Plasma

Serum

Other: _____

Do you prefer a specific coagulant?

Yes

No

If yes, which coagulant do you prefer?

Li-Hep

K2-EDTA

K3-EDTA

Citrate

Other: _____

What is the cost per test you can accept?

< 1 Euro

< 10 Euro

< 100 Euro

< 1000 Euro

How many preparation steps would you tolerate?

< 2

< 5

< 10

> 10

Other: _____

How many preparation steps you perform in your work for a standard analysis?

< 2

< 5

< 10

> 10

Other: _____

Which preparation steps do you tolerate?

What is the qualification level of the operator to use the instrument?

	Yes	No
Lab technician	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Lab engineer	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Clinician	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

If your answer is Other. Please specify.

What level of user experience do you expect?

Trained expert only

Simple use for non-trained personnel

At which cost you can buy the detection kit?

< 100 Euro

100 < <500 Euro

500 < <1000 Euro

>1000 Euro

Which time to result do you expect from such a test?

What Sensitivity do you expect from such a measurement?

What Specificity do you expect from such a measurement?

Instrument / Device

Do you want an automated system?

Yes

No

What's the degree of automation?

Manual

Semi- Automated

Fully-Automated

Do you want a point of care device?

Yes

No

Do you need the device to be transportable?

Yes

No

What system dimensions you accept?

Handheld (15x10x15 cm)

POC (20x15x20 cm)

Microwave (40x40x40 cm)

I don't care

What connectivity would you prefer?

LAN (local area network)

WLAN (Wireless local area network)

Other: _____

What system weight you accept?

- < 2 kg
- < 5 kg
- < 15 kg
- I don't care

Which price you are able to pay for the system?

- < 5 KEuro
- < 10 KEuro
- < 20 KEuro
- Other: _____

Which sensitivity you are targeting?

- μM
- nM
- pM
- fM

You need a fixed temperature?

- Yes
- No

If Yes. Which temperature?

If No. Which temperature range?

- 4< <25 Celsius
- 15< <40 Celsius
- 15< <60 Celsius
- 15< <90 Celsius
- Other: _____

What kind of result do you prefer?

	Yes	No
Semi-quantitative	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Quantitative	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Questions for policy makers / finances

Health insurances. Would you prefer to finance

- Sensor device (investment)
- Sensor chips (consumable)

Hospital/Lab administration

	Yes	No
Selection (bidding procedure) and purchase procedures for new equipment?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

BIOCDx Device/ End-users Questionnaire

This is a survey on end-users requirements and needs from a Point-of-Care (PoC) device for cancer detection.

Email address *

[REDACTED]

End-user information

Organization/Company name *

[REDACTED]

Role - Field of expertise *

PhD candidate-Breast cancer

Country

Switzerland

Questionnaire

Application

Which cancer types are you interested in?

- Breast
- Prostate
- Lung
- GI tract
- Hematopoietic malignancies
- Skin
- Soft tissue sarcomas
- Melanoma
- Brain
- Urinary tract

Do you want to detect many biomarkers simultaneously?

- Yes
- No

How many biomarkers you want to detect?

- 1 biomarker
- < 5 biomarkers

For you application, would you prefer a disposable cartridge? *

- Yes
- No

How long you want to store the cartridge? *

- < 3 months
- 3 months < <6 months
- > 6 months

Do you prefer to reuse the cartridge?

- Yes
- No

If you prefer to reuse the cartridge. How many times?

- 1 < <5
- 5 < <10
- 10 < <20

You are interested in:

- Progression
- Relapse
- Early diagnosis
- Therapeutic response
- Other: _____

Test

How many samples do you want to test per day (the speed of the analysis)?

- < 50
- < 250
- < 500
- < 1000
- Other: _____

What analysis duration do you expect?

- < 5 min
- < 1 hour
- < 5 hours
- < 10 hours
- Other: _____

Which maximal sample volume do you tolerate for each analysis?

- < 5 μL
- < 100 μL
- < 500 μL
- < 1 mL
- Other: <10 ml _____

Which sample type do you want to analyse?

- Whole Blood
- Plasma
- Serum
- Other: _____

Do you prefer a specific sample type?

Whole Blood

Plasma

Serum

Other: _____

Do you prefer a specific coagulant?

Yes

No

If yes, which coagulant do you prefer?

Li-Hep

K2-EDTA

K3-EDTA

Citrate

Other: _____

What is the cost per test you can accept?

< 1 Euro

< 10 Euro

< 100 Euro

< 1000 Euro

How many preparation steps would you tolerate?

< 2

< 5

< 10

> 10

Other: _____

How many preparation steps you perform in your work for a standard analysis?

< 2

< 5

< 10

> 10

Other: _____

Which preparation steps do you tolerate?

What is the qualification level of the operator to use the instrument?

	Yes	No
Lab technician	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Lab engineer	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Clinician	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

If your answer is Other. Please specify.

What level of user experience do you expect?

Trained expert only

Simple use for non-trained personnel

At which cost you can buy the detection kit?

< 100 Euro

100< <500 Euro

500< <1000 Euro

>1000 Euro

Which time to result do you expect from such a test?

24 h

What Sensitivity do you expect from such a measurement?

High

What Specificity do you expect from such a measurement?

High

Instrument / Device

Do you want an automated system?

Yes

No

What's the degree of automation?

Manual

Semi- Automated

Fully-Automated

Do you want a point of care device?

Yes

No

Do you need the device to be transportable?

Yes

No

What system dimensions you accept?

Handheld (15x10x15 cm)

POC (20x15x20 cm)

Microwave (40x40x40 cm)

I don't care

What connectivity would you prefer?

LAN (local area network)

WLAN (Wireless local area network)

Other: _____

What system weight you accept?

- < 2 kg
- < 5 kg
- < 15 kg
- I don't care

Which price you are able to pay for the system?

- < 5 KEuro
- < 10 KEuro
- < 20 KEuro
- Other: _____

Which sensitivity you are targeting?

- μM
- nM
- pM
- fM

You need a fixed temperature?

- Yes
- No

If Yes. Which temperature?

If No. Which temperature range?

- 4< <25 Celsius
- 15< <40 Celsius
- 15< <60 Celsius
- 15< <90 Celsius
- Other: _____

What kind of result do you prefer?

	Yes	No
Semi-quantitative	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Quantitative	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Questions for policy makers / finances

Health insurances. Would you prefer to finance

- Sensor device (investment)
- Sensor chips (consumable)

Hospital/Lab administration

	Yes	No
Selection (bidding procedure) and purchase procedures for new equipment?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

BIOCDx Device/ End-users Questionnaire

This is a survey on end-users requirements and needs from a Point-of-Care (PoC) device for cancer detection.

Email address *

End-user information

Organization/Company name *

Role - Field of expertise *

Head of the Department

Country

Greece

Questionnaire

Application

Which cancer types are you interested in?

- Breast
- Prostate
- Lung
- GI tract
- Hematopoietic malignancies
- Skin
- Soft tissue sarcomas
- Melanoma
- Brain
- Urinary tract

Do you want to detect many biomarkers simultaneously?

- Yes
- No

How many biomarkers you want to detect?

- 1 biomarker
- < 5 biomarkers

For you application, would you prefer a disposable cartridge? *

- Yes
- No

How long you want to store the cartridge? *

- < 3 months
- 3 months < <6 months
- > 6 months

Do you prefer to reuse the cartridge?

- Yes
- No

If you prefer to reuse the cartridge. How many times?

- 1 < <5
- 5 < <10
- 10 < <20

You are interested in:

- Progression
- Relapse
- Early diagnosis
- Therapeutic response
- Other: _____

Test

How many samples do you want to test per day (the speed of the analysis)?

< 50

< 250

< 500

< 1000

Other: _____

What analysis duration do you expect?

< 5 min

< 1 hour

< 5 hours

< 10 hours

Other: _____

Which maximal sample volume do you tolerate for each analysis?

< 5 μL

< 100 μL

< 500 μL

< 1 mL

Other: _____

Which sample type do you want to analyse?

Whole Blood

Plasma

Serum

Other: _____

Do you prefer a specific sample type?

Whole Blood

Plasma

Serum

Other: _____

Do you prefer a specific coagulant?

Yes

No

If yes, which coagulant do you prefer?

Li-Hep

K2-EDTA

K3-EDTA

Citrate

Other: _____

What is the cost per test you can accept?

< 1 Euro

< 10 Euro

< 100 Euro

< 1000 Euro

How many preparation steps would you tolerate?

< 2

< 5

< 10

> 10

Other: _____

How many preparation steps you perform in your work for a standard analysis?

< 2

< 5

< 10

> 10

Other: _____

Which preparation steps do you tolerate?

< 10 _____

What is the qualification level of the operator to use the instrument?

	Yes	No
Lab technician	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Lab engineer	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Clinician	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

If your answer is Other. Please specify.

What level of user experience do you expect?

Trained expert only

Simple use for non-trained personnel

At which cost you can buy the detection kit?

< 100 Euro

100< <500 Euro

500< <1000 Euro

>1000 Euro

Which time to result do you expect from such a test?

< 2 days

What Sensitivity do you expect from such a measurement?

> 90%

What Specificity do you expect from such a measurement?

> 90%

Instrument / Device

Do you want an automated system?

Yes

No

What's the degree of automation?

Manual

Semi- Automated

Fully-Automated

Do you want a point of care device?

Yes

No

Do you need the device to be transportable?

Yes

No

What system dimensions you accept?

Handheld (15x10x15 cm)

POC (20x15x20 cm)

Microwave (40x40x40 cm)

I don't care

What connectivity would you prefer?

LAN (local area network)

WLAN (Wireless local area network)

Other: _____

What system weight you accept?

- < 2 kg
- < 5 kg
- < 15 kg
- I don't care

Which price you are able to pay for the system?

- < 5 KEuro
- < 10 KEuro
- < 20 KEuro
- Other: _____

Which sensitivity you are targeting?

- μM
- nM
- pM
- fM

You need a fixed temperature?

- Yes
- No

If Yes. Which temperature?

If No. Which temperature range?

- 4< <25 Celsius
- 15< <40 Celsius
- 15< <60 Celsius
- 15< <90 Celsius
- Other: _____

What kind of result do you prefer?

	Yes	No
Semi-quantitative	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Quantitative	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>

Questions for policy makers / finances

Health insurances. Would you prefer to finance

- Sensor device (investment)
- Sensor chips (consumable)

Hospital/Lab administration

	Yes	No
Selection (bidding procedure) and purchase procedures for new equipment?	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

BIOCDx Device/ End-users Questionnaire

This is a survey on end-users requirements and needs from a Point-of-Care (PoC) device for cancer detection.

Email address *

End-user information

Organization/Company name *

Role - Field of expertise *

Intern at Medical Oncology

Country

Greece

Questionnaire

Application

Which cancer types are you interested in?

- Breast
- Prostate
- Lung
- GI tract
- Hematopoietic malignancies
- Skin
- Soft tissue sarcomas
- Melanoma
- Brain
- Urinary tract

Do you want to detect many biomarkers simultaneously?

- Yes
- No

How many biomarkers you want to detect?

- 1 biomarker
- < 5 biomarkers

For you application, would you prefer a disposable cartridge? *

- Yes
- No

How long you want to store the cartridge? *

- < 3 months
- 3 months < <6 months
- > 6 months

Do you prefer to reuse the cartridge?

- Yes
- No

If you prefer to reuse the cartridge. How many times?

- 1 < <5
- 5 < <10
- 10 < <20

You are interested in:

- Progression
- Relapse
- Early diagnosis
- Therapeutic response
- Other: _____

Test

How many samples do you want to test per day (the speed of the analysis)?

- < 50
- < 250
- < 500
- < 1000
- Other: _____

What analysis duration do you expect?

- < 5 min
- < 1 hour
- < 5 hours
- < 10 hours
- Other: _____

Which maximal sample volume do you tolerate for each analysis?

- < 5 μL
- < 100 μL
- < 500 μL
- < 1 mL
- Other: _____

Which sample type do you want to analyse?

- Whole Blood
- Plasma
- Serum
- Other: _____

Do you prefer a specific sample type?

Whole Blood

Plasma

Serum

Other: _____

Do you prefer a specific coagulant?

Yes

No

If yes, which coagulant do you prefer?

Li-Hep

K2-EDTA

K3-EDTA

Citrate

Other: _____

What is the cost per test you can accept?

< 1 Euro

< 10 Euro

< 100 Euro

< 1000 Euro

How many preparation steps would you tolerate?

- < 2
- < 5
- < 10
- > 10
- Other: _____

How many preparation steps you perform in your work for a standard analysis?

- < 2
- < 5
- < 10
- > 10
- Other: _____

Which preparation steps do you tolerate?

What is the qualification level of the operator to use the instrument?

	Yes	No
Lab technician	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Lab engineer	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Clinician	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

If your answer is Other. Please specify.

What level of user experience do you expect?

Trained expert only

Simple use for non-trained personnel

At which cost you can buy the detection kit?

< 100 Euro

100< <500 Euro

500< <1000 Euro

>1000 Euro

Which time to result do you expect from such a test?

2-3 days

What Sensitivity do you expect from such a measurement?

70%

What Specificity do you expect from such a measurement?

90%

Instrument / Device

Do you want an automated system?

Yes

No

What's the degree of automation?

Manual

Semi- Automated

Fully-Automated

Do you want a point of care device?

Yes

No

Do you need the device to be transportable?

Yes

No

What system dimensions you accept?

Handheld (15x10x15 cm)

POC (20x15x20 cm)

Microwave (40x40x40 cm)

I don't care

What connectivity would you prefer?

LAN (local area network)

WLAN (Wireless local area network)

Other: _____

What system weight you accept?

- < 2 kg
- < 5 kg
- < 15 kg
- I don't care

Which price you are able to pay for the system?

- < 5 KEuro
- < 10 KEuro
- < 20 KEuro
- Other: _____

Which sensitivity you are targeting?

- μM
- nM
- pM
- fM

You need a fixed temperature?

- Yes
- No

If Yes. Which temperature?

If No. Which temperature range?

- 4< <25 Celsius
- 15< <40 Celsius
- 15< <60 Celsius
- 15< <90 Celsius
- Other: _____

What kind of result do you prefer?

	Yes	No
Semi-quantitative	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Quantitative	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Questions for policy makers / finances

Health insurances. Would you prefer to finance

- Sensor device (investment)
- Sensor chips (consumable)

Hospital/Lab administration

	Yes	No
Selection (bidding procedure) and purchase procedures for new equipment?	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

BIOCDx Device/ End-users Questionnaire

This is a survey on end-users requirements and needs from a Point-of-Care (PoC) device for cancer detection.

Email address *

[REDACTED]

End-user information

Organization/Company name *

[REDACTED]

Role - Field of expertise *

INTERNIST

Country

Greece

Questionnaire

Application

Which cancer types are you interested in?

- Breast
- Prostate
- Lung
- GI tract
- Hematopoietic malignancies
- Skin
- Soft tissue sarcomas
- Melanoma
- Brain
- Urinary tract

Do you want to detect many biomarkers simultaneously?

- Yes
- No

How many biomarkers you want to detect?

- 1 biomarker
- < 5 biomarkers

For you application, would you prefer a disposable cartridge? *

- Yes
- No

How long you want to store the cartridge? *

- < 3 months
- 3 months < <6 months
- > 6 months

Do you prefer to reuse the cartridge?

- Yes
- No

If you prefer to reuse the cartridge. How many times?

- 1 < <5
- 5 < <10
- 10 < <20

You are interested in:

- Progression
- Relapse
- Early diagnosis
- Therapeutic response
- Other: _____

Test

How many samples do you want to test per day (the speed of the analysis)?

- < 50
- < 250
- < 500
- < 1000
- Other: _____

What analysis duration do you expect?

- < 5 min
- < 1 hour
- < 5 hours
- < 10 hours
- Other: _____

Which maximal sample volume do you tolerate for each analysis?

- < 5 μL
- < 100 μL
- < 500 μL
- < 1 mL
- Other: _____

Which sample type do you want to analyse?

- Whole Blood
- Plasma
- Serum
- Other: _____

Do you prefer a specific sample type?

Whole Blood

Plasma

Serum

Other: _____

Do you prefer a specific coagulant?

Yes

No

If yes, which coagulant do you prefer?

Li-Hep

K2-EDTA

K3-EDTA

Citrate

Other: _____

What is the cost per test you can accept?

< 1 Euro

< 10 Euro

< 100 Euro

< 1000 Euro

How many preparation steps would you tolerate?

- < 2
- < 5
- < 10
- > 10
- Other: _____

How many preparation steps you perform in your work for a standard analysis?

- < 2
- < 5
- < 10
- > 10
- Other: _____

Which preparation steps do you tolerate?

What is the qualification level of the operator to use the instrument?

	Yes	No
Lab technician	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Lab engineer	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Clinician	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Other	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

If your answer is Other. Please specify.

Biologist

What level of user experience do you expect?

Trained expert only

Simple use for non-trained personnel

At which cost you can buy the detection kit?

< 100 Euro

100 < < 500 Euro

500 < < 1000 Euro

> 1000 Euro

Which time to result do you expect from such a test?

1 day

What Sensitivity do you expect from such a measurement?

>80%

What Specificity do you expect from such a measurement?

>95%

Instrument / Device

Do you want an automated system?

Yes

No

What's the degree of automation?

Manual

Semi- Automated

Fully-Automated

Do you want a point of care device?

Yes

No

Do you need the device to be transportable?

Yes

No

What system dimensions you accept?

Handheld (15x10x15 cm)

POC (20x15x20 cm)

Microwave (40x40x40 cm)

I don't care

What connectivity would you prefer?

LAN (local area network)

WLAN (Wireless local area network)

Other: _____

What system weight you accept?

- < 2 kg
- < 5 kg
- < 15 kg
- I don't care

Which price you are able to pay for the system?

- < 5 KEuro
- < 10 KEuro
- < 20 KEuro
- Other: _____

Which sensitivity you are targeting?

- μM
- nM
- pM
- fM

You need a fixed temperature?

- Yes
- No

If Yes. Which temperature?

15-40 celsius _____

If No. Which temperature range?

- 4< <25 Celsius
- 15< <40 Celsius
- 15< <60 Celsius
- 15< <90 Celsius
- Other: _____

What kind of result do you prefer?

	Yes	No
Semi-quantitative	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Quantitative	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>

Questions for policy makers / finances

Health insurances. Would you prefer to finance

- Sensor device (investment)
- Sensor chips (consumable)

Hospital/Lab administration

	Yes	No
Selection (bidding procedure) and purchase procedures for new equipment?	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

BIOCDx Device/ End-users Questionnaire

This is a survey on end-users requirements and needs from a Point-of-Care (PoC) device for cancer detection.

Email address *

[REDACTED]

End-user information

Organization/Company name *

[REDACTED]

Role - Field of expertise *

Medical Oncology

Country

Greece

Questionnaire

Application

Which cancer types are you interested in?

- Breast
- Prostate
- Lung
- GI tract
- Hematopoietic malignancies
- Skin
- Soft tissue sarcomas
- Melanoma
- Brain
- Urinary tract

Do you want to detect many biomarkers simultaneously?

- Yes
- No

How many biomarkers you want to detect?

- 1 biomarker
- < 5 biomarkers

For you application, would you prefer a disposable cartridge? *

- Yes
- No

How long you want to store the cartridge? *

- < 3 months
- 3 months < <6 months
- > 6 months

Do you prefer to reuse the cartridge?

- Yes
- No

If you prefer to reuse the cartridge. How many times?

- 1 < <5
- 5 < <10
- 10 < <20

You are interested in:

- Progression
- Relapse
- Early diagnosis
- Therapeutic response

Other: _____

Test

How many samples do you want to test per day (the speed of the analysis)?

- < 50
- < 250
- < 500
- < 1000
- Other: _____

What analysis duration do you expect?

- < 5 min
- < 1 hour
- < 5 hours
- < 10 hours
- Other: _____

Which maximal sample volume do you tolerate for each analysis?

- < 5 μL
- < 100 μL
- < 500 μL
- < 1 mL
- Other: _____

Which sample type do you want to analyse?

- Whole Blood
- Plasma
- Serum
- Other: _____

Do you prefer a specific sample type?

Whole Blood

Plasma

Serum

Other: _____

Do you prefer a specific coagulant?

Yes

No

If yes, which coagulant do you prefer?

Li-Hep

K2-EDTA

K3-EDTA

Citrate

Other: _____

What is the cost per test you can accept?

< 1 Euro

< 10 Euro

< 100 Euro

< 1000 Euro

How many preparation steps would you tolerate?

< 2

< 5

< 10

> 10

Other: _____

How many preparation steps you perform in your work for a standard analysis?

< 2

< 5

< 10

> 10

Other: _____

Which preparation steps do you tolerate?

any _____

What is the qualification level of the operator to use the instrument?

	Yes	No
Lab technician	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Lab engineer	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Clinician	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

If your answer is Other. Please specify.

What level of user experience do you expect?

Trained expert only

Simple use for non-trained personnel

At which cost you can buy the detection kit?

< 100 Euro

100< <500 Euro

500< <1000 Euro

>1000 Euro

Which time to result do you expect from such a test?

4 days

What Sensitivity do you expect from such a measurement?

>90 %

What Specificity do you expect from such a measurement?

95 %

Instrument / Device

Do you want an automated system?

Yes

No

What's the degree of automation?

Manual

Semi- Automated

Fully-Automated

Do you want a point of care device?

Yes

No

Do you need the device to be transportable?

Yes

No

What system dimensions you accept?

Handheld (15x10x15 cm)

POC (20x15x20 cm)

Microwave (40x40x40 cm)

I don't care

What connectivity would you prefer?

LAN (local area network)

WLAN (Wireless local area network)

Other: _____

What system weight you accept?

- < 2 kg
- < 5 kg
- < 15 kg
- I don't care

Which price you are able to pay for the system?

- < 5 KEuro
- < 10 KEuro
- < 20 KEuro
- Other: _____

Which sensitivity you are targeting?

- μM
- nM
- pM
- fM

You need a fixed temperature?

- Yes
- No

If Yes. Which temperature?

If No. Which temperature range?

- 4< <25 Celsius
- 15< <40 Celsius
- 15< <60 Celsius
- 15< <90 Celsius
- Other: _____

What kind of result do you prefer?

	Yes	No
Semi-quantitative	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Quantitative	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Questions for policy makers / finances

Health insurances. Would you prefer to finance

- Sensor device (investment)
- Sensor chips (consumable)

Hospital/Lab administration

	Yes	No
Selection (bidding procedure) and purchase procedures for new equipment?	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

BIOCDx Device/ End-users Questionnaire

This is a survey on end-users requirements and needs from a Point-of-Care (PoC) device for cancer detection.

Email address *

[REDACTED]

End-user information

Organization/Company name *

[REDACTED]

Role - Field of expertise *

Pathologist, Medical Oncologist

Country

Greece

Questionnaire

Application

Which cancer types are you interested in?

- Breast
- Prostate
- Lung
- GI tract
- Hematopoietic malignancies
- Skin
- Soft tissue sarcomas
- Melanoma
- Brain
- Urinary tract

Do you want to detect many biomarkers simultaneously?

- Yes
- No

How many biomarkers you want to detect?

- 1 biomarker
- < 5 biomarkers

For you application, would you prefer a disposable cartridge? *

- Yes
- No

How long you want to store the cartridge? *

- < 3 months
- 3 months < <6 months
- > 6 months

Do you prefer to reuse the cartridge?

- Yes
- No

If you prefer to reuse the cartridge. How many times?

- 1 < <5
- 5 < <10
- 10 < <20

You are interested in:

- Progression
- Relapse
- Early diagnosis
- Therapeutic response
- Other: _____

Test

How many samples do you want to test per day (the speed of the analysis)?

- < 50
- < 250
- < 500
- < 1000
- Other: _____

What analysis duration do you expect?

- < 5 min
- < 1 hour
- < 5 hours
- < 10 hours
- Other: _____

Which maximal sample volume do you tolerate for each analysis?

- < 5 μL
- < 100 μL
- < 500 μL
- < 1 mL
- Other: _____

Which sample type do you want to analyse?

- Whole Blood
- Plasma
- Serum
- Other: _____

Do you prefer a specific sample type?

Whole Blood

Plasma

Serum

Other: _____

Do you prefer a specific coagulant?

Yes

No

If yes, which coagulant do you prefer?

Li-Hep

K2-EDTA

K3-EDTA

Citrate

Other: _____

What is the cost per test you can accept?

< 1 Euro

< 10 Euro

< 100 Euro

< 1000 Euro

How many preparation steps would you tolerate?

< 2

< 5

< 10

> 10

Other: _____

How many preparation steps you perform in your work for a standard analysis?

< 2

< 5

< 10

> 10

Other: _____

Which preparation steps do you tolerate?

What is the qualification level of the operator to use the instrument?

	Yes	No
Lab technician	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Lab engineer	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Clinician	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Other	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

If your answer is Other. Please specify.

What level of user experience do you expect?

Trained expert only

Simple use for non-trained personnel

At which cost you can buy the detection kit?

< 100 Euro

100 < < 500 Euro

500 < < 1000 Euro

> 1000 Euro

Which time to result do you expect from such a test?

1 day

What Sensitivity do you expect from such a measurement?

> 95%

What Specificity do you expect from such a measurement?

> 99%

Instrument / Device

Do you want an automated system?

Yes

No

What's the degree of automation?

Manual

Semi- Automated

Fully-Automated

Do you want a point of care device?

Yes

No

Do you need the device to be transportable?

Yes

No

What system dimensions you accept?

Handheld (15x10x15 cm)

POC (20x15x20 cm)

Microwave (40x40x40 cm)

I don't care

What connectivity would you prefer?

LAN (local area network)

WLAN (Wireless local area network)

Other: _____

What system weight you accept?

- < 2 kg
- < 5 kg
- < 15 kg
- I don't care

Which price you are able to pay for the system?

- < 5 KEuro
- < 10 KEuro
- < 20 KEuro
- Other: _____

Which sensitivity you are targeting?

- μM
- nM
- pM
- fM

You need a fixed temperature?

- Yes
- No

If Yes. Which temperature?

If No. Which temperature range?

- 4< <25 Celsius
- 15< <40 Celsius
- 15< <60 Celsius
- 15< <90 Celsius
- Other: _____

What kind of result do you prefer?

	Yes	No
Semi-quantitative	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Quantitative	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Questions for policy makers / finances

Health insurances. Would you prefer to finance

- Sensor device (investment)
- Sensor chips (consumable)

Hospital/Lab administration

	Yes	No
Selection (bidding procedure) and purchase procedures for new equipment?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

BIOCDx Device/ End-users Questionnaire

This is a survey on end-users requirements and needs from a Point-of-Care (PoC) device for cancer detection.

Email address *

[REDACTED]

End-user information

Organization/Company name *

[REDACTED]

Role - Field of expertise *

medical Oncologist

Country

Greece

Questionnaire

Application

Which cancer types are you interested in?

- Breast
- Prostate
- Lung
- GI tract
- Hematopoietic malignancies
- Skin
- Soft tissue sarcomas
- Melanoma
- Brain
- Urinary tract

Do you want to detect many biomarkers simultaneously?

- Yes
- No

How many biomarkers you want to detect?

- 1 biomarker
- < 5 biomarkers

For you application, would you prefer a disposable cartridge? *

- Yes
- No

How long you want to store the cartridge? *

- < 3 months
- 3 months < <6 months
- > 6 months

Do you prefer to reuse the cartridge?

- Yes
- No

If you prefer to reuse the cartridge. How many times?

- 1 < <5
- 5 < <10
- 10 < <20

You are interested in:

- Progression
- Relapse
- Early diagnosis
- Therapeutic response
- Other: _____

Test

How many samples do you want to test per day (the speed of the analysis)?

< 50

< 250

< 500

< 1000

Other: _____

What analysis duration do you expect?

< 5 min

< 1 hour

< 5 hours

< 10 hours

Other: _____

Which maximal sample volume do you tolerate for each analysis?

< 5 μL

< 100 μL

< 500 μL

< 1 mL

Other: _____

Which sample type do you want to analyse?

Whole Blood

Plasma

Serum

Other: _____

Do you prefer a specific sample type?

Whole Blood

Plasma

Serum

Other: _____

Do you prefer a specific coagulant?

Yes

No

If yes, which coagulant do you prefer?

Li-Hep

K2-EDTA

K3-EDTA

Citrate

Other: _____

What is the cost per test you can accept?

< 1 Euro

< 10 Euro

< 100 Euro

< 1000 Euro

How many preparation steps would you tolerate?

- < 2
- < 5
- < 10
- > 10
- Other: _____

How many preparation steps you perform in your work for a standard analysis?

- < 2
- < 5
- < 10
- > 10
- Other: _____

Which preparation steps do you tolerate?

Blood draw _____

What is the qualification level of the operator to use the instrument?

	Yes	No
Lab technician	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Lab engineer	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Clinician	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

If your answer is Other. Please specify.

Biologist

What level of user experience do you expect?

Trained expert only

Simple use for non-trained personnel

At which cost you can buy the detection kit?

< 100 Euro

100< <500 Euro

500< <1000 Euro

>1000 Euro

Which time to result do you expect from such a test?

1 day

What Sensitivity do you expect from such a measurement?

> 80%

What Specificity do you expect from such a measurement?

> 95%

Instrument / Device

Do you want an automated system?

Yes

No

What's the degree of automation?

Manual

Semi- Automated

Fully-Automated

Do you want a point of care device?

Yes

No

Do you need the device to be transportable?

Yes

No

What system dimensions you accept?

Handheld (15x10x15 cm)

POC (20x15x20 cm)

Microwave (40x40x40 cm)

I don't care

What connectivity would you prefer?

LAN (local area network)

WLAN (Wireless local area network)

Other: _____

What system weight you accept?

- < 2 kg
- < 5 kg
- < 15 kg
- I don't care

Which price you are able to pay for the system?

- < 5 KEuro
- < 10 KEuro
- < 20 KEuro
- Other: _____

Which sensitivity you are targeting?

- μM
- nM
- pM
- fM

You need a fixed temperature?

- Yes
- No

If Yes. Which temperature?

If No. Which temperature range?

- 4< <25 Celsius
- 15< <40 Celsius
- 15< <60 Celsius
- 15< <90 Celsius
- Other: _____

What kind of result do you prefer?

	Yes	No
Semi-quantitative	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Quantitative	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Questions for policy makers / finances

Health insurances. Would you prefer to finance

- Sensor device (investment)
- Sensor chips (consumable)

Hospital/Lab administration

	Yes	No
Selection (bidding procedure) and purchase procedures for new equipment?	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

BIOCDx Device/ End-users Questionnaire

This is a survey on end-users requirements and needs from a Point-of-Care (PoC) device for cancer detection.

Email address *

[REDACTED]

End-user information

Organization/Company name *

[REDACTED]

Role - Field of expertise *

Head of the Department- Medical Oncologist

Country

Greece

Questionnaire

Application

Which cancer types are you interested in?

- Breast
- Prostate
- Lung
- GI tract
- Hematopoietic malignancies
- Skin
- Soft tissue sarcomas
- Melanoma
- Brain
- Urinary tract

Do you want to detect many biomarkers simultaneously?

- Yes
- No

How many biomarkers you want to detect?

- 1 biomarker
- < 5 biomarkers

For you application, would you prefer a disposable cartridge? *

- Yes
- No

How long you want to store the cartridge? *

- < 3 months
- 3 months < <6 months
- > 6 months

Do you prefer to reuse the cartridge?

- Yes
- No

If you prefer to reuse the cartridge. How many times?

- 1 < <5
- 5 < <10
- 10 < <20

You are interested in:

- Progression
- Relapse
- Early diagnosis
- Therapeutic response
- Other: _____

Test

How many samples do you want to test per day (the speed of the analysis)?

- < 50
- < 250
- < 500
- < 1000
- Other: _____

What analysis duration do you expect?

- < 5 min
- < 1 hour
- < 5 hours
- < 10 hours
- Other: _____

Which maximal sample volume do you tolerate for each analysis?

- < 5 μL
- < 100 μL
- < 500 μL
- < 1 mL
- Other: _____

Which sample type do you want to analyse?

- Whole Blood
- Plasma
- Serum
- Other: _____

Do you prefer a specific sample type?

Whole Blood

Plasma

Serum

Other: _____

Do you prefer a specific coagulant?

Yes

No

If yes, which coagulant do you prefer?

Li-Hep

K2-EDTA

K3-EDTA

Citrate

Other: _____

What is the cost per test you can accept?

< 1 Euro

< 10 Euro

< 100 Euro

< 1000 Euro

How many preparation steps would you tolerate?

< 2

< 5

< 10

> 10

Other: _____

How many preparation steps you perform in your work for a standard analysis?

< 2

< 5

< 10

> 10

Other: _____

Which preparation steps do you tolerate?

What is the qualification level of the operator to use the instrument?

	Yes	No
Lab technician	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Lab engineer	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Clinician	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

If your answer is Other. Please specify.

What level of user experience do you expect?

Trained expert only

Simple use for non-trained personnel

At which cost you can buy the detection kit?

< 100 Euro

100 < < 500 Euro

500 < < 1000 Euro

> 1000 Euro

Which time to result do you expect from such a test?

<1h

What Sensitivity do you expect from such a measurement?

>80%

What Specificity do you expect from such a measurement?

>80%

Instrument / Device

Do you want an automated system?

Yes

No

What's the degree of automation?

Manual

Semi- Automated

Fully-Automated

Do you want a point of care device?

Yes

No

Do you need the device to be transportable?

Yes

No

What system dimensions you accept?

Handheld (15x10x15 cm)

POC (20x15x20 cm)

Microwave (40x40x40 cm)

I don't care

What connectivity would you prefer?

LAN (local area network)

WLAN (Wireless local area network)

Other: _____

What system weight you accept?

- < 2 kg
- < 5 kg
- < 15 kg
- I don't care

Which price you are able to pay for the system?

- < 5 KEuro
- < 10 KEuro
- < 20 KEuro
- Other: _____

Which sensitivity you are targeting?

- μM
- nM
- pM
- fM

You need a fixed temperature?

- Yes
- No

If Yes. Which temperature?

Room temperature _____

If No. Which temperature range?

- 4< <25 Celsius
- 15< <40 Celsius
- 15< <60 Celsius
- 15< <90 Celsius
- Other: _____

What kind of result do you prefer?

	Yes	No
Semi-quantitative	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Quantitative	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Questions for policy makers / finances

Health insurances. Would you prefer to finance

- Sensor device (investment)
- Sensor chips (consumable)

Hospital/Lab administration

	Yes	No
Selection (bidding procedure) and purchase procedures for new equipment?	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

BIOCDx Device/ End-users Questionnaire

This is a survey on end-users requirements and needs from a Point-of-Care (PoC) device for cancer detection.

Email address *

[REDACTED]

End-user information

Organization/Company name *

[REDACTED]

Role - Field of expertise *

Medical Oncologist

Country

Greece

Questionnaire

Application

Which cancer types are you interested in?

- Breast
- Prostate
- Lung
- GI tract
- Hematopoietic malignancies
- Skin
- Soft tissue sarcomas
- Melanoma
- Brain
- Urinary tract

Do you want to detect many biomarkers simultaneously?

- Yes
- No

How many biomarkers you want to detect?

- 1 biomarker
- < 5 biomarkers

For you application, would you prefer a disposable cartridge? *

- Yes
- No

How long you want to store the cartridge? *

- < 3 months
- 3 months < <6 months
- > 6 months

Do you prefer to reuse the cartridge?

- Yes
- No

If you prefer to reuse the cartridge. How many times?

- 1 < <5
- 5 < <10
- 10 < <20

You are interested in:

- Progression
- Relapse
- Early diagnosis
- Therapeutic response
- Other: _____

Test

How many samples do you want to test per day (the speed of the analysis)?

- < 50
- < 250
- < 500
- < 1000
- Other: _____

What analysis duration do you expect?

- < 5 min
- < 1 hour
- < 5 hours
- < 10 hours
- Other: _____

Which maximal sample volume do you tolerate for each analysis?

- < 5 μL
- < 100 μL
- < 500 μL
- < 1 mL
- Other: _____

Which sample type do you want to analyse?

- Whole Blood
- Plasma
- Serum
- Other: _____

Do you prefer a specific sample type?

Whole Blood

Plasma

Serum

Other: _____

Do you prefer a specific coagulant?

Yes

No

If yes, which coagulant do you prefer?

Li-Hep

K2-EDTA

K3-EDTA

Citrate

Other: _____

What is the cost per test you can accept?

< 1 Euro

< 10 Euro

< 100 Euro

< 1000 Euro

How many preparation steps would you tolerate?

< 2

< 5

< 10

> 10

Other: All required

How many preparation steps you perform in your work for a standard analysis?

< 2

< 5

< 10

> 10

Other: _____

Which preparation steps do you tolerate?

What is the qualification level of the operator to use the instrument?

	Yes	No
Lab technician	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Lab engineer	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Clinician	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

If your answer is Other. Please specify.

What level of user experience do you expect?

Trained expert only

Simple use for non-trained personnel

At which cost you can buy the detection kit?

< 100 Euro

100 < <500 Euro

500 < <1000 Euro

>1000 Euro

Which time to result do you expect from such a test?

What Sensitivity do you expect from such a measurement?

What Specificity do you expect from such a measurement?

Instrument / Device

Do you want an automated system?

Yes

No

What's the degree of automation?

Manual

Semi- Automated

Fully-Automated

Do you want a point of care device?

Yes

No

Do you need the device to be transportable?

Yes

No

What system dimensions you accept?

Handheld (15x10x15 cm)

POC (20x15x20 cm)

Microwave (40x40x40 cm)

I don't care

What connectivity would you prefer?

LAN (local area network)

WLAN (Wireless local area network)

Other: _____

What system weight you accept?

- < 2 kg
- < 5 kg
- < 15 kg
- I don't care

Which price you are able to pay for the system?

- < 5 KEuro
 - < 10 KEuro
 - < 20 KEuro
 - Other: no estimation
-

Which sensitivity you are targeting?

- μM
- nM
- pM
- fM

You need a fixed temperature?

- Yes
- No

If Yes. Which temperature?

If No. Which temperature range?

- 4< <25 Celsius
- 15< <40 Celsius
- 15< <60 Celsius
- 15< <90 Celsius
- Other: _____

What kind of result do you prefer?

	Yes	No
Semi-quantitative	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Quantitative	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Questions for policy makers / finances

Health insurances. Would you prefer to finance

- Sensor device (investment)
- Sensor chips (consumable)

Hospital/Lab administration

	Yes	No
Selection (bidding procedure) and purchase procedures for new equipment?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

BIOCDx Device/ End-users Questionnaire

This is a survey on end-users requirements and needs from a Point-of-Care (PoC) device for cancer detection.

Email address *

End-user information

Organization/Company name *

Role - Field of expertise *

dermatoloog, huidkanker onderzoeker

Country

Nederland

Questionnaire

Application

Which cancer types are you interested in?

- Breast
- Prostate
- Lung
- GI tract
- Hematopoietic malignancies
- Skin
- Soft tissue sarcomas
- Melanoma
- Brain
- Urinary tract

Do you want to detect many biomarkers simultaneously?

- Yes
- No

How many biomarkers you want to detect?

- 1 biomarker
- < 5 biomarkers

For you application, would you prefer a disposable cartridge? *

- Yes
- No

How long you want to store the cartridge? *

- < 3 months
- 3 months < <6 months
- > 6 months

Do you prefer to reuse the cartridge?

- Yes
- No

If you prefer to reuse the cartridge. How many times?

- 1 < <5
- 5 < <10
- 10 < <20

You are interested in:

- Progression
- Relapse
- Early diagnosis
- Therapeutic response
- Other: prognosis / metastatic behavior

Test

How many samples do you want to test per day (the speed of the analysis)?

- < 50
- < 250
- < 500
- < 1000
- Other: _____

What analysis duration do you expect?

- < 5 min
- < 1 hour
- < 5 hours
- < 10 hours
- Other: _____

Which maximal sample volume do you tolerate for each analysis?

- < 5 μL
- < 100 μL
- < 500 μL
- < 1 mL
- Other: _____

Which sample type do you want to analyse?

- Whole Blood
- Plasma
- Serum
- Other: _____

Do you prefer a specific sample type?

Whole Blood

Plasma

Serum

Other: _____

Do you prefer a specific coagulant?

Yes

No

If yes, which coagulant do you prefer?

Li-Hep

K2-EDTA

K3-EDTA

Citrate

Other: _____

What is the cost per test you can accept?

< 1 Euro

< 10 Euro

< 100 Euro

< 1000 Euro

How many preparation steps would you tolerate?

< 2

< 5

< 10

> 10

Other: _____

How many preparation steps you perform in your work for a standard analysis?

< 2

< 5

< 10

> 10

Other: _____

Which preparation steps do you tolerate?

What is the qualification level of the operator to use the instrument?

	Yes	No
Lab technician	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Lab engineer	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Clinician	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

If your answer is Other. Please specify.

What level of user experience do you expect?

- Trained expert only
- Simple use for non-trained personnel

At which cost you can buy the detection kit?

- < 100 Euro
- 100< <500 Euro
- 500< <1000 Euro
- >1000 Euro

Which time to result do you expect from such a test?

within a week

What Sensitivity do you expect from such a measurement?

>90%

What Specificity do you expect from such a measurement?

> 50%

Instrument / Device

Do you want an automated system?

Yes

No

What's the degree of automation?

Manual

Semi- Automated

Fully-Automated

Do you want a point of care device?

Yes

No

Do you need the device to be transportable?

Yes

No

What system dimensions you accept?

Handheld (15x10x15 cm)

POC (20x15x20 cm)

Microwave (40x40x40 cm)

I don't care

What connectivity would you prefer?

LAN (local area network)

WLAN (Wireless local area network)

Other: _____

What system weight you accept?

- < 2 kg
- < 5 kg
- < 15 kg
- I don't care

Which price you are able to pay for the system?

- < 5 KEuro
- < 10 KEuro
- < 20 KEuro
- Other: _____

Which sensitivity you are targeting?

- μM
- nM
- pM
- fM

You need a fixed temperature?

- Yes
- No

If Yes. Which temperature?

If No. Which temperature range?

- 4< <25 Celsius
- 15< <40 Celsius
- 15< <60 Celsius
- 15< <90 Celsius
- Other: _____

What kind of result do you prefer?

	Yes	No
Semi-quantitative	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Quantitative	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Questions for policy makers / finances

Health insurances. Would you prefer to finance

- Sensor device (investment)
- Sensor chips (consumable)

Hospital/Lab administration

	Yes	No
Selection (bidding procedure) and purchase procedures for new equipment?	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

BIOCDx Device/ End-users Questionnaire

This is a survey on end-users requirements and needs from a Point-of-Care (PoC) device for cancer detection.

Email address *

End-user information

Organization/Company name *

Role - Field of expertise *

Sub Investigator

Country

Greece

Questionnaire

Application

Which cancer types are you interested in?

- Breast
- Prostate
- Lung
- GI tract
- Hematopoietic malignancies
- Skin
- Soft tissue sarcomas
- Melanoma
- Brain
- Urinary tract

Do you want to detect many biomarkers simultaneously?

- Yes
- No

How many biomarkers you want to detect?

- 1 biomarker
- < 5 biomarkers

For you application, would you prefer a disposable cartridge? *

- Yes
- No

How long you want to store the cartridge? *

- < 3 months
- 3 months < <6 months
- > 6 months

Do you prefer to reuse the cartridge?

- Yes
- No

If you prefer to reuse the cartridge. How many times?

- 1 < <5
- 5 < <10
- 10 < <20

You are interested in:

- Progression
- Relapse
- Early diagnosis
- Therapeutic response
- Other: _____

Test

How many samples do you want to test per day (the speed of the analysis)?

- < 50
- < 250
- < 500
- < 1000
- Other: _____

What analysis duration do you expect?

- < 5 min
- < 1 hour
- < 5 hours
- < 10 hours
- Other: _____

Which maximal sample volume do you tolerate for each analysis?

- < 5 μL
- < 100 μL
- < 500 μL
- < 1 mL
- Other: _____

Which sample type do you want to analyse?

- Whole Blood
- Plasma
- Serum
- Other: _____

Do you prefer a specific sample type?

Whole Blood

Plasma

Serum

Other: _____

Do you prefer a specific coagulant?

Yes

No

If yes, which coagulant do you prefer?

Li-Hep

K2-EDTA

K3-EDTA

Citrate

Other: _____

What is the cost per test you can accept?

< 1 Euro

< 10 Euro

< 100 Euro

< 1000 Euro

How many preparation steps would you tolerate?

< 2

< 5

< 10

> 10

Other: _____

How many preparation steps you perform in your work for a standard analysis?

< 2

< 5

< 10

> 10

Other: _____

Which preparation steps do you tolerate?

What is the qualification level of the operator to use the instrument?

	Yes	No
Lab technician	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>
Lab engineer	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Clinician	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

If your answer is Other. Please specify.

What level of user experience do you expect?

Trained expert only

Simple use for non-trained personnel

At which cost you can buy the detection kit?

< 100 Euro

100 < <500 Euro

500 < <1000 Euro

>1000 Euro

Which time to result do you expect from such a test?

What Sensitivity do you expect from such a measurement?

What Specificity do you expect from such a measurement?

Instrument / Device

Do you want an automated system?

Yes

No

What's the degree of automation?

Manual

Semi- Automated

Fully-Automated

Do you want a point of care device?

Yes

No

Do you need the device to be transportable?

Yes

No

What system dimensions you accept?

Handheld (15x10x15 cm)

POC (20x15x20 cm)

Microwave (40x40x40 cm)

I don't care

What connectivity would you prefer?

LAN (local area network)

WLAN (Wireless local area network)

Other: _____

What system weight you accept?

- < 2 kg
- < 5 kg
- < 15 kg
- I don't care

Which price you are able to pay for the system?

- < 5 KEuro
- < 10 KEuro
- < 20 KEuro
- Other: _____

Which sensitivity you are targeting?

- μM
- nM
- pM
- fM

You need a fixed temperature?

- Yes
- No

If Yes. Which temperature?

If No. Which temperature range?

- 4< <25 Celsius
- 15< <40 Celsius
- 15< <60 Celsius
- 15< <90 Celsius
- Other: _____

What kind of result do you prefer?

	Yes	No
Semi-quantitative	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Quantitative	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Questions for policy makers / finances

Health insurances. Would you prefer to finance

- Sensor device (investment)
- Sensor chips (consumable)

Hospital/Lab administration

	Yes	No
Selection (bidding procedure) and purchase procedures for new equipment?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

BIOCDx Device/ End-users Questionnaire

This is a survey on end-users requirements and needs from a Point-of-Care (PoC) device for cancer detection.

Email address *

[Redacted]

End-user information

Organization/Company name *

[Redacted]

Role - Field of expertise *

Doctor

Country

Greece

Questionnaire

Application

Which cancer types are you interested in?

- Breast
- Prostate
- Lung
- GI tract
- Hematopoietic malignancies
- Skin
- Soft tissue sarcomas
- Melanoma
- Brain
- Urinary tract

Do you want to detect many biomarkers simultaneously?

- Yes
- No

How many biomarkers you want to detect?

- 1 biomarker
- < 5 biomarkers

For you application, would you prefer a disposable cartridge? *

- Yes
- No

How long you want to store the cartridge? *

- < 3 months
- 3 months < <6 months
- > 6 months

Do you prefer to reuse the cartridge?

- Yes
- No

If you prefer to reuse the cartridge. How many times?

- 1 < <5
- 5 < <10
- 10 < <20

You are interested in:

- Progression
- Relapse
- Early diagnosis
- Therapeutic response
- Other: _____

Test

How many samples do you want to test per day (the speed of the analysis)?

- < 50
- < 250
- < 500
- < 1000
- Other: _____

What analysis duration do you expect?

- < 5 min
- < 1 hour
- < 5 hours
- < 10 hours
- Other: _____

Which maximal sample volume do you tolerate for each analysis?

- < 5 μL
- < 100 μL
- < 500 μL
- < 1 mL
- Other: _____

Which sample type do you want to analyse?

- Whole Blood
- Plasma
- Serum
- Other: _____

Do you prefer a specific sample type?

Whole Blood

Plasma

Serum

Other: _____

Do you prefer a specific coagulant?

Yes

No

If yes, which coagulant do you prefer?

Li-Hep

K2-EDTA

K3-EDTA

Citrate

Other: _____

What is the cost per test you can accept?

< 1 Euro

< 10 Euro

< 100 Euro

< 1000 Euro

How many preparation steps would you tolerate?

- < 2
- < 5
- < 10
- > 10
- Other: _____

How many preparation steps you perform in your work for a standard analysis?

- < 2
- < 5
- < 10
- > 10
- Other: _____

Which preparation steps do you tolerate?

What is the qualification level of the operator to use the instrument?

	Yes	No
Lab technician	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Lab engineer	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Clinician	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

If your answer is Other. Please specify.

What level of user experience do you expect?

Trained expert only

Simple use for non-trained personnel

At which cost you can buy the detection kit?

< 100 Euro

100 < < 500 Euro

500 < < 1000 Euro

> 1000 Euro

Which time to result do you expect from such a test?

What Sensitivity do you expect from such a measurement?

What Specificity do you expect from such a measurement?

Instrument / Device

Do you want an automated system?

Yes

No

What's the degree of automation?

Manual

Semi- Automated

Fully-Automated

Do you want a point of care device?

Yes

No

Do you need the device to be transportable?

Yes

No

What system dimensions you accept?

Handheld (15x10x15 cm)

POC (20x15x20 cm)

Microwave (40x40x40 cm)

I don't care

What connectivity would you prefer?

LAN (local area network)

WLAN (Wireless local area network)

Other: _____

What system weight you accept?

- < 2 kg
- < 5 kg
- < 15 kg
- I don't care

Which price you are able to pay for the system?

- < 5 KEuro
- < 10 KEuro
- < 20 KEuro
- Other: _____

Which sensitivity you are targeting?

- μM
- nM
- pM
- fM

You need a fixed temperature?

- Yes
- No

If Yes. Which temperature?

If No. Which temperature range?

- 4< <25 Celsius
- 15< <40 Celsius
- 15< <60 Celsius
- 15< <90 Celsius
- Other: _____

What kind of result do you prefer?

	Yes	No
Semi-quantitative	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Quantitative	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Questions for policy makers / finances

Health insurances. Would you prefer to finance

- Sensor device (investment)
- Sensor chips (consumable)

Hospital/Lab administration

	Yes	No
Selection (bidding procedure) and purchase procedures for new equipment?	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>